

Evaluation Questionnaire for DCR Networks

Short background:

The evaluation of DCR networks is designed as a qualitative study following the concepts of grounded theory (J. Corbin and A. Strauss. Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory). The questions are grouped into general questions, contextualization, actions and consequences. The general questions are meant to provide an idea about the expertise of the participant and to highlight the relevance of the investigated approach, whereas the contextualization, actions and consequences questions are used to investigate the processes associated with modeling the law before and after the introduction of DCR networks and its impact on different aspects such as understandability, maintainability, communication and productivity.

I. General questions

Objectives:

Obtain an idea about the participant expertise in using the DCR graphs and the relevance of modeling references between law paragraphs in practice.

Questions:

- Approximately how many hours a week you spend creating DCR models?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 01:45	"3 or 4 a week ... since Fall 2017"

- How often are you required to maintain (i.e., edit or update) process models after being developed?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 01:59	It starts with a high frequency and as they move toward a step where the graph is more stable, the frequency of maintenance decreases
Part1 02:27	How do you model processes? "It starts by receiving some material about the process itself and that could be a law text or a process description, then I review that and probably do a prototype, then have a meeting with the domain expert ... that would be the social worker or the local team manager ... and then depending if the domain expert has viewed DCR Graphs earlier, we can then create the graph during the meeting as we speak about the process ... no no, we refine the graph and after that I may go home and refine a bit more and do some simulations and see if I get the result I need ... then depending on the quality of the second prototype, we will have a meeting again with the domain expert and then do some simulation to verify if the graph is were it should be and its ready for

	deployment. Then, we will do a testing in the open case manager just to verify that all the technicalities are working”
Part1 04:45	What is the difference between the first refinement you do with domain expert and the one you do afterwards? “if I have a feeling that I created too many activities, then I reduce it also most of the time I don’t spend time creating the forms so I will do that afterwards ... cleaning”
Part1 05:50	When you are with the domain experts what artifacts do you use to explain them the process? “Only the DCR, and simulation as well but that would be at the second prototype” “... the first and second prototypes [contain] most likely, the simple constraint relation ... for example condition relation and maybe include and exclude in a low matter, and then with the refinement I will do add-ons to obtain the scenarios that I want to create”
Part1 07:28	How frequent do you usually update a model once deployed in the open case manager? “6 times ... after deployment ... for paragraph 27”
Part1 08:34	Types of maintenance tasks: “the first one was some changes in the activities and that could be the title of the activity because the title is viewed in the open case manager” “its more about add-ones to the process [extending the process] ” “we have been speaking about some part of the graph that we need to change, but before I can change, I need to figure about how to maintain the data structure as well, so I could be aligned”

- When modeling the law, how common is it to find paragraphs referring to each other?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 10:40	“with the graphs that I have been creating, almost everyone”

- Why is it relevant to consider the references between law paragraphs when modeling them?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 11:45	“the sections of law text we are working in, they are kind of connected in a way that when this paragraph is finished then you start something else, so the result of this paragraph is connected to other paragraphs as well” [example in audio] [another situation] “[having another] process that runs in parallel ... [showcase example in 2020-02-07_13h47_08.mp4]”

II. Contextualization

Objectives:

- Elicit the past modeling experience of the participant with the previously used approach
- Identify the most re-occurring challenges associated with the previously used approach
- Identify the work around practices associated with the previously used approach
- Investigate the Impact of the previously used approach on understandability, maintainability, communication and productivity

Questions:

- Before the introduction of DCR networks (or so called global events), how did you model references between law paragraphs? Do you have an example in the DCR portal which you can refer to?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 16:10	“the global events create an opportunity to do some automations ... so within the graph, I would automatically create this process because I know it is going to happen ... (1) before global events, I would ask the user the create the graph ... (->) sometimes they don’t create the graph and then they do the work besides the open case manager ... (->) the possibly to collect the timeline of [the whole] case [is lost]”
Part1 28:30	“ (2) this graph is a whole chapter of the law text so that would be multiple paragraphs within one graph” [meaning that before DCR networks they used to combine many paragraphs into one process model] (->) “When we create a graph right now we are much more thinking about the process more than what the paragraphs says, but when we are creating the graph we align that we are complying to the law text so the graph is more process oriented than describing the law ... when creating graphs right now we only looking at one law text but within that they are sections from other laws that are represented but they are hidden within the process that we are going through” [the participant explains that this way might cause some modeling redundancies in the future]
Part1 38:40	(->) [The idea of combining graphs did not workout because of] “the complexity and because of the knowledge that they would be 2 other processes that would be created within [that graph] ... they would be too many activities and a bit too crowded, you wouldn’t be able to read the graph at all ... and also for my own clarification and structure of the graph and the connection between the different processes”

- Could you think of examples of specific processes that were hard or unfeasible to model using the tradional approach? What issues did you face following this traditional approach?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 35:40	“the first one is that we couldn’t start the other graph ... we couldn’t create communication between two graphs”

- What work around practices, if any, did you use to bypass these issues?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 17:00	(1) before global events, I would ask the user the create the graph ... (>) sometimes they don’t create the graph and then they do the work besides the open case manager

- Assuming you could combine related law paragraphs (e.g., into a single process model)
(1) How complex was it for you to explain these models and use them a basis for communication with other co-workers? why?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 40:30	"it is not possible to communicate from this graph ... even an experienced modeler can't find the start events and the end because it's too crowded and it is not refined in a way of a reading pattern"

(3) How complex was it for you to maintain (i.e., edit, alter) these models after being developed? why?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 45:30	"it would be difficult I think ... because the canvas would be so big to see the constraints and the constraints would overlap"

- In which ways, if any, this traditional approach influenced your productivity (in terms of time, effort, errors, need for support from the DCR team, rework)?

Timestamp	Insight
Part1 45:50	"yes, that was also a kind of journey and learning experience in our journey ... DCR was still new for me"

III. Actions

Objectives:

- Identify the perceived features and benefits of DCR networks
- Investigate how easy is to familiarize with the notions of DCR Networks
- Understand how a participant uses DCR networks to model a specific process
- Investigate the clearness of the semantics of DCR networks
- Investigate the support provided by the existing DCR tools to model references between models
- Investigate the expressiveness of DCR networks
- Identify other potential benefits and challenges associated with the use of DCR networks
- Identify the key aspects which could be improved with regards to DCR networks

Questions:

- What features/capabilities does DCR networks provide?

Timestamp	Insight
Part2 00:20	"it should be able to reduce the complexity of the graph ... because of can then take sections [referring to section of law paragraphs] out of the graph and place it to another graph" "the second thing is that it contributes to give the ability to communicate between graphs so you can activate a graph at a certain stage"
Part2 04:00	Since the introduction of DCR networks, how much did you use this concept to model the law? "well at least in 3 of the ... more or less in everyone we have some sort of global activities"
Part2 04:30	Can you mention some law paragraphs where it is used? "we have chapter 27 about the notification ... 152, 153, 154, 155 ... they are within one graph, they are sort of connected to paragraph 11 section 1, section 2, section 3 and soon paragraph 52a and also paragraph 50 ... they are linked [through global events mechanism] with paragraph 27"

-Did you have any modelling situations which are practically impossible with DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part2 07:28	“at some point or some state, it will be difficult to maintain the relations between the graphs ... the references ... because of the complexity of the law itself, so ... as we are now the domain expert can be in doubt in which paragraphs are connected to which paragraphs ... we will probably not certain but probably end there”
Part2 08:56	In your opinion how can we overcome this problem? “a view within the design or the portal, the global activity would have ... some symbol on the activity to showcase that this is a global activity ... that would only showcase that here it is but it doesn’t showcase what you are communicate to or where it’s linked or referred to”

- How complex was it for you to familiarize/learn about the semantics of DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part2 11:45	“the link is as I know is not restrict by relations but the global activities, so the global activity has to be executable in both graphs before I can do it, but the link activity doesn’t care about; doesn’t have to be executable in both graphs .. and that’s kind of hard for me”

- When getting started with DCR networks, how often did you require support from the DCR team and what aspects were problematic for you? how do that evolve?

Timestamp	Insight
Part2 13:30	“at the beginning yes ... just for clarification more or less ... and also in different scenarios where the graph didn’t behave as I thought it should be because of the restriction or the relation in the one graph I was not aware of, so it wasn’t executable in one graph but was in the first graph” “... then I tested, from there I knew I have to be aware that in the other graph it should also have to be executable, and then probably why I don’t build that many conditions on global activities”

- How confident do you feel with the semantics of the DCR networks? which aspects are clear to you? and which aspects are still confusing?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 00:46	“In general, within DCR networks [referring to linking] I’m still a bit insecure about that ... [interviewer asking: how about references?] “I’m more confident for that yes”

- Which aspects do you think are currently missing or would be important to improve with regards to the semantics of DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 00:58	"it is not possible to transport or communicate data ... for example if you have an activity that contains a date, you can't transfer that to the other graph"

- In which aspects are the DCR tools (e.g., process modeler, open case manager) helping you to implement relations between the law paragraphs?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 02:53	- "it is not possible to test without the open case manager ..." - "we don't get the simulation history within the graph or within the designer, so it is not possible to do the control: is this scenario still available [meaning there is no support for test cases yet]" - "the control for dead-ends is not possible [meaning that he cannot run the path analyzer when using references between graphs]"

- Which aspects do you think are currently missing or would be important to improve with regards to the tools allowing you to create and test references between models?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 06:10	- "The zoom-out ability to see the connection between graphs" - "the simulation between" - "the path analyzer" - "the recommendation tool ... where it recommends what activities, you should do as a next activity ... based on history of simulations"

- Have you faced any limitations with regards to the use of DCR networks to model references between law paragraphs? in other words, are there any processes which you still couldn't model with DCR networks?

- Which aspects do you think are currently missing or would be important to improve to allow modeling the processes which could not currently be modeled with DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 07:42	"not that I'm aware of yet, no"

- Do you have any further comments about the benefits or the challenges associated with the use of DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 09:23	"I think I still face the limitation of a better way of creating the global activity ... because at this point when I model, I only see the end door, so I only see the door. I create the door, but I cannot see what's on the other side when I do the model. It is also a bit risky due to [unclear] its line of text, so the only reference between is the "global" [referring to a label added in the activity ID to create a reference] and the name that identify it. So, if you spell it wrong or add something then you lose the connection, so there is some insecurity in the way it is built right now ... it would easier to create a graph with reference if it's more visible"

- Do you have any other suggestions with regards to missing aspects or aspects that could be improved in DCR networks?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 18:22	“in the designer, I would say the development of the extra tools so they are familiar with forms in the path analyzer”

IV. Consequences:

Objectives:

- Investigate possible impacts of DCR networks on modeling tasks
- Investigate the Impact of DCR networks on understandability, maintainability, communication and productivity

Questions:

- Does DCR networks somehow make other modelling tasks more difficult?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 19:40	<p>The modeling issues are demonstrated in “screenCast1.mp4”</p> <p>-Summary:</p> <p>(1) It is hard to maintain and to reconcile the graphs in the network independently of each other</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Model2</p> </div> </div> <p>Meaning: Activity3 in Model 1 makes Activity5 in Model 2 pending</p>

(3) Refining models into fragments can be done into several ways. Still, it is hard to know which fragmentation results in understandable models.

Meaning: Activity6-G in Model 1 makes Activity5 in Model 2 pending
 (The behavior is similar to the one shown in (2))

e.g., The example above is similar to the one shown in (2) in term of behavior. While it optimizes the number of constraints and activities, it becomes hard to interpret Model 1 independently of Model 2.

- Considering your use of DCR networks to model references between process models:

(1) How easy is it for you to explain these models and to use them as a basis for communication with other co-workers? why?

Timestamp	Insight
Part3 32:14	“the understandability [referring to DCR networks] is a bit more complex for the user”
Part3 33:30	“I think I have done it once ... showcased the communication between two graphs in which case I could see the receiver confusion”
Part3 34:08	“I still think that we are on an expert level and we still have to think about that the one who is receiving is a novice”

(2) How easy is it for you to maintain (i.e., edit, alter) these models after being developed? why?

Timestamp	Insight
	<i>See the answer to the question “Does DCR networks somehow make other modelling tasks more difficult?”</i>